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**COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE INCIDENCE
OF MALIGNANT NEOPLASMS IN THE POPULATION
OF GRODNO AND GOMEL REGIONS OF THE REPUBLIC
OF BELARUS (2010-2019)**

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Annotation: A comparative assessment of the dynamics and average annual rates of the incidence of malignant neoplasms of different localization and mortality among the population of the Republic of Belarus (Gomel and Grodno regions) for the period 2010-2019 was carried out. As a result of the conducted studies, a trend of a significant increase in oncological pathology in the population of Gomel and Grodno regions in the period 2010-2019 was established. The increase in morbidity is largely determined by the unfavorable direction of demographic processes in Belarus associated with the "aging" of the population. It has been established that the incidence of malignant neoplasms of the urban population is higher than that of the rural population. The morbidity and mortality of men with malignant neoplasms of all localizations is generally always higher than that of women.

Keywords: morbidity, mortality, oncological pathology

СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ЗАБОЛЕВАЕМОСТИ ЗЛОКАЧЕСТВЕННЫМИ НОВООБРАЗОВАНИЯМИ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ ГРОДНЕНСКОЙ И ГОМЕЛЬСКОЙ ОБЛАСТЕЙ РЕСПУБЛИКИ БЕЛАРУСЬ (2010–2019)

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Аннотация: Проведена сравнительная оценка динамики и среднегодовых темпов показателей заболеваемости злокачественными новообразованиями разной локализации и смертности среди населения Республике Беларусь (Гомельской и Гродненской областей), за период 2010-2019 г. В результате проведенных исследований установлена тенденция значительного роста онкологической патологии у населения Гомельской и Гродненской областей в период 2010-2019. Прирост заболеваемости в значительной мере определен неблагоприятным направлением демографических процессов в Беларуси, связанными с «постарением» населения. Установлено, что заболеваемость злокачественными новообразованиями городского населения выше, чем сельского. Заболеваемость и смертность мужчин злокачественными новообразованиями всех локализаций в целом всегда выше, чем женщин.

Keywords: заболеваемость, смертность, онкологическая патология

Relevance. The problems of clinical oncology remain in the focus of attention of medical professionals around the world due to the constant increase in the incidence of malignant tumors and mortality from them. The relevance of this disease is determined by its high prevalence. At the end of 2020, the International Agency for the Study of Malignant Neoplasms presented new data on morbidity in 185 countries: the number of new cases in

2020 reached 19.3 million, and 10 million people died from this disease. Every fifth inhabitant of the planet will be diagnosed with cancer during his lifetime; every eighth man and every 11 women will die from this disease. Based on medical and statistical studies, it was found that 100 years ago one out of 30 people got cancer, 50 years ago – one out of 15, currently every fifth or sixth person gets sick [1]. The annual growth rate of patients with malignant neoplasms is approximately 2 %, which exceeds the growth of the world population by 0.3-0.5 %. The forecast of WHO experts is disappointing: cancer incidence worldwide will increase to 24 million cases by 2050, and mortality to 16 million. annually registered cases. In Belarus, as in the world, the number of cancer patients is constantly growing. According to official statistics, more than 40 thousand patients have been registered annually in our country since 2011, and since 2017 – more than 50 thousand patients with a cancer diagnosis for the first time in their lives, which is about 0.5% of the country's population. In 2018, 48,900 new cases of cancer were recorded, in 2019 – 49,930. In the last two years, there has been a significant decrease in cancer incidence in Belarus – by 25 % at once, but this is due to the pandemic, people are less likely to turn to specialists [1, 2, 6].

The significant growth rate of morbidity, high mortality and severity of disability make the problem of prevention, successful diagnosis and treatment of this pathology extremely important and urgent at the present time.

The purpose of the study. The purpose of this work was a comparative assessment of the dynamics and average annual rates of incidence of malignant neoplasms of different localization and mortality among the population of the Republic of Belarus (Gomel and Grodno regions), for the period 2010-2019.

Material and methods of research. The object of the study was information on the number of newly registered cases of cancer in the Republic of Belarus (Gomel and Grodno regions), obtained from the official statistical collection "Healthcare in the Republic of Belarus" for the period under study, as well as data from the Belarusian Cancer Register. The work uses epidemiological, comparative-evaluation and analytical methods to study official statistical data on the health status of the population of the Grodno and Gomel regions of the Republic of Belarus, as well as literature data on morbidity and mortality of residents of our country from malignant neoplasms.

Results and their discussion. In Belarus, over 10 years (2010-2019), statistics on oncological diseases increased by 15 %, while at the same time,

mortality decreased by 1.8 %. In 2010, 187 people per 100 thousand of the population died from cancer, in 2019 – 184 people per 100 thousand of the population. In Belarus, in 2010-2019, the number of daily registered diseases with malignant neoplasms increased by an average of 1,181 cases per year. In 2019 (based on the BCR database as of 01.05.2020) 54203 new cases of malignant neoplasms were registered. There were 231293 patients on dispensary control at the end of 2010, 315151 patients at the end of 2019. The increase was 36.3 %. The dynamics of morbidity in our country for the period from 2010 to 2019, a significant increase in primary morbidity per 100 thousand population was registered in the class "Malignant neoplasms": in 2010 – 459.1; in 2011 – 465.6; in 2012 – 456,8; 2013 – 464,9; 2014 – 484,3; 2015 – 513,4; 2016 – 521,9; 2017 – 537.8; in 2018 – 554,5; 2019 – 572,6 [3]. In the period from 2010 to 2019, the average annual increase in morbidity was 2.7 %. Over 10 years, this indicator has grown by 24.7 %, among the able-bodied – 29.0 %. The increase in the number of diseases for every 100,000 men over 10 years was 25.8%, and women – 23.6 %. The incidence among urban residents has increased by 25.5 % in 10 years, and in rural areas by 23.8 %. At the same time, the dynamics of the morbidity of the working-age population differs significantly from the morbidity of the entire population. Thus, the increase in the incidence of rural residents of working age was 2.1 times higher than the increase in the incidence of urban residents (respectively +50.5% and +23.9 %). Against the background of the general increase in morbidity, an increase in the differences between the morbidity of urban and rural residents was noted: in 2010, the morbidity of rural residents of working age was 11.2% higher than the morbidity of urban residents, and in 2019 – by 35.2 %. In rural areas, the influence of unfavorable factors accelerating the increase in the incidence of malignant neoplasms is significantly increasing. With a uniform increase in morbidity, the annual excess of its levels in rural areas remains, which is associated with a greater proportion of elderly and elderly people (including due to the migration of the able-bodied population from villages to cities. In 2019, the proportion of people over 60 years of age was 20.5% among urban and 29.3 % among rural residents [4].

The analysis of rough intensive morbidity indicators of the entire population of Belarus revealed significant differences in dynamics for neoplasms of various organs. A particularly noticeable increase over 10 years occurred due to prostate cancer – by 67.5%; skin melanoma – by 51.4 %, skin cancer (including basal cell carcinoma) – by 46.7 %, oral and pharyngeal

tumors – by 45.2 %, liver – 40.9 and pancreas – by 40.2 %. Negative dynamics was noted for malignant neoplasms: lips (-36.4 %), bone sarcomas (-20.0 %), Hodgkin's disease (-13.3 %), stomach cancer (-12.6 %), cervix (-2.7 %), leukemia (-0.9 %) and lung cancer (-0.5 %). In the country, prostate cancer, lung and colorectal cancer were most often detected in men, breast cancer, colorectal and cervical cancer in women. This structure of diseases has been observed for more than 4-5 years. If we talk about mortality from cancer, men most often died from lung cancer, colorectal cancer and stomach cancer, women – from breast cancer, colorectal cancer and stomach cancer. At the same time, the peak incidence of breast cancer is 49 years old, colorectal cancer is 70 years old. In Belarusians, the number of colorectal cancer detections (16.1 %) also equaled the number of breast cancer detections (16.2 %). Among men of working age, the incidence of all forms of malignant neoplasms for the period 2010-2019. increased from 237.7 to 317.8 per 100,000 male population. The increase in morbidity was 33.7 %. Among women of working age, the incidence increased from 211.3 to 259.4 per 100,000 female population. An increase of 22.8 % [3].

During this period, there is a tendency to decrease mortality from malignant neoplasms. For an objective assessment of cancer control, mortality rates for diseases are used. Their analysis shows that for 10 years the gap between the levels of morbidity and mortality continues to increase, which indicates positive changes in the state of cancer care to the population. The ratio of intensive mortality rates to morbidity of the entire population of the country decreased from 40.8 % in 2010. up to 34.7 % – in 2019, and for the working-age population – from 36.5 % to 31.6 %. The survival rate of rural residents is statistically significantly lower than that of urban residents (60.7 ± 0.1 % and 51.0 ± 0.3 %) [4].

There are certain differences in the overall cancer incidence in Belarus and in the regions of the republic. From year to year, the highest cancer incidence remains in the Gomel region. The absolute number of newly detected cases of malignant neoplasms in the Gomel region for 10 years: 2010 – 7204; 2011 – 7155; 2012 – 6724; 2013 – 6982; 2014 – 7445; 2015 – 7533; 2016 – 8002; 2017 – 8393; 2018 – 8920; 2019 – 8739. The absolute average annual increase is 171. The dynamics of the incidence of malignant neoplasms per 100 thousand population: in 2010 – 501.3; in 2011 – 499.5; in 2012 – 470.6; 2013 – 489.4; 2014 – 522.5; 2015 – 529.2; 2016 – 562.8; 2017 – 591.8; in 2018 – 631.4; 2019 – 621.4. and 10 years this indicator has increased by 24

%. In the period from 2010 to 2019, the average annual growth rate is 3.2 %. The incidence of the population of the Gomel region with malignant neoplasms of the main locations per 100,000 population: a particularly noticeable increase over 10 years occurred due to prostate cancer – 51.2 (2010) – 127.4 (2019); breast cancer – 79.0 (2010) – 103.2 (2019); skin melanoma – 8.0 (2010) – 10.6 (2019); skin cancer (including basal cell carcinoma) – 78.5 (2010) – 104.7 (2019); oral and pharyngeal tumors – 15.5 (2010) – 21.2 (2019); larynx – 6.1 (2010) – 8.6 (2019); liver – 4.2 (2010) – 8.2 (2019); pancreas – 10.5 (2010) – 15.3 (2019); esophagus – 5.3 (2010) – 7.3 (2019); colon – 25.9 (2010) – 33.4; (2019); rectum – 21.0 (2010) – 25.5 (2019); uterine bodies – 33.4 (2010) – 47.9 (2019); kidneys – 22.6 (2010) – 31.8 (2019); thyroid gland – 11.1 (2010) – 16.2 (2019). Negative dynamics was noted for malignant neoplasms: lips – 3.4 (2010) – 2.6 (2019); bone sarcomas – 0.9 (2010) – 0.4 (2019); Hodgkin's disease – 3.2 (2010) – 1.1 (2019); stomach cancer – 38.3 (2010) – 30.5 (2019); cervix – 18.9 (2010) – 15.4 (2019); leukemia – 11.8 (2010) – 10.7 (2019); lung cancer – 52.8 (2010) – 52.4 (2019) [4]. Analyzing the data, I would like to pay special attention to the increase in the incidence of malignant neoplasms: skin (including basal cell carcinoma), pancreas, thyroid gland, prostate gland in men, breast in women in the Gomel region. Of the patients who became ill in 2019, 1124 patients died during 2020 from the moment of diagnosis, which corresponds to about 1/5 of the number of patients with a diagnosis of malignant formation for the first time in their lives.

In Grodno in 1990, 13 thousand people were registered, today more than 32 thousand, i.e. every 32nd resident of the region. The absolute number of newly detected cases of malignant neoplasms in the Grodno region for 10 years: 2010 – 4726; 2011 – 4812; 2012 – 4564; 2013 – 4698; 2014 – 4778; 2015 – 5060; 2016 – 5350; 2017 – 5316; 2018 – 5345; 2019 – 5788. The absolute average annual increase is 118. The dynamics of morbidity over 10 years (2010-2019) with malignant neoplasms per 100 thousand population: in 2010 – 442.2; in 2011 – 452.4; in 2012 – 430,6; 2013 – 444,6; 2014 – 453,4; 2015 – 481,3; 2016 – 510,1; 2017 – 508,4; in 2018 – 513.2; 2019 – 558.1. The average annual growth rate was 2.6% [4]. The incidence of the population of the Grodno region with malignant neoplasms of the main locations per 100,000 population: a particularly noticeable increase over 10 years occurred due to: prostate cancer – 57.8 (2010) – 96.2 (2019); breast cancer – 79.0 (2010) – 95.1 (2019); skin melanoma – 6.3 (2010) – 9.4 (2019); skin cancer (including basal

cell carcinoma) – 62.1 (2010) – 108.1 (2019); oral and pharyngeal tumors – 14.9 (2010) – 20.1 (2019); larynx – 7.5 (2010) – 8.4 (2019); liver – 4.4 (2010) – 5.9 (2019); pancreas – 9.3 (2010) – 11.4 (2019); esophagus – 6.0 (2010) – 7.5 (2019); colon – 24.8 (2010) – 32.0; (2019); rectum – 25.0 (2010) – 25.7 (2019); uterine bodies – 28.4 (2010) – 45.2 (2019); kidneys – 20.0 (2010) – 29.5 (2019); thyroid gland – 5.4 (2010) – 6.5 (2019); bone sarcomas – 0.9 (2010) – 1.5 (2019). Negative dynamics was noted for malignant neoplasms: lips – 1.4 (2010) – 1.3 (2019); Hodgkin's disease – 3.5 (2010) – 3.0 (2019); stomach cancer – 30.1 (2010) – 27.4 (2019); cervix – 16.6 (2010) – 15.7 (2019); leukemia – 13.2 (2010) – 13.1 (2019); cancer lung – 44.4 (2010) – 40.8 (2019) [3].

Analyzing the data, I would like to pay special attention to the increase in the incidence of malignant neoplasms of the skin in men and women, prostate in men, breast in women in the Grodno region. The mortality rate from malignant neoplasms in 2019 was 185.1 per 100,000 population [5, 6].

Conclusions. As a result of the conducted studies, a trend of a significant increase in oncological pathology in the population of Gomel and Grodno regions in the period 2010-2019 was established. The increase in morbidity is largely determined by the unfavorable direction of demographic processes in Belarus associated with the "aging" of the population. It has been established that the incidence of malignant neoplasms of the urban population is higher than that of the rural population. The morbidity and mortality of men with malignant neoplasms of all localizations is generally always higher than that of women. Gomel Region is a leader in oncological diseases in the Republic of Belarus.

As a result, over 10 years, the incidence of malignant neoplasms increased by 24.7 %, and the number of patients registered at the dispensary increased by 36.3 %. Nevertheless, the mortality rate decreased by 1.8 %, and the long-term results of treatment significantly improved. Over the past 10 years, the gap between morbidity and mortality continues to increase, which indicates positive changes in the state of cancer care to the population. The ratio of intensive mortality rates to morbidity of the entire population of the country decreased from 40.8 % in 2010. up to 34.7 % – in 2019, and for the working-age population – from 36.5 % to 31.6 %. The situation is significantly improving due to the improvement of medical work, technical re-equipment of specialized medical institutions, the introduction of protocols for the diagnosis and treatment of cancer patients. The fact that the survival rate of rural

residents is statistically significantly lower than that of urban residents (60.7 ± 0.1 % and 51.0 ± 0.3 %) is fundamental for the organization of cancer control. The existing differences are due to shortcomings in the medical examination of patients living in rural areas, which leads to late diagnosis of relapses of diseases, different levels of technical equipment and qualifications of medical personnel.

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